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Telehealth for Chronic Disease Management among Older Adults in Nigeria: Exploring the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

¹Alaku Ifeanyi; ²Nma-Njoku Alexandra Chukwu; ³Alaku Emeka & ⁴Ngwoke Chidiebere Mercy

^{1,2}Department of Social Work, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria
ifeanyi.alaku.191754@unn.edu.ng; Nma.njoku@unn.edu.ng

³Department of Sociology, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria
emekaalaku@gmail.com

⁴College of Nursing Science and Health Technology, Nsukka, Nigeria
mercynngwokec@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Healthcare systems face serious problems as a result of the rising incidence of chronic illnesses among older adults, especially in low-resource environments like Nigeria. Continuous monitoring and control are crucial as the aging population is more likely to suffer from diseases including diabetes, hypertension, and heart disease. Enhancing the treatment of chronic diseases in older persons can be achieved through telehealth, which is the use of information and communication technology to provide healthcare services remotely. This study investigates how telehealth can increase access to healthcare in Nigeria, lower travel obstacles, and improve health outcomes. In order to comprehend older adults' acceptance and possible obstacles to telehealth adoption, the study employs the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and focuses on two important factors: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). The study used a literature review approach, gathering pertinent information on telehealth and TAM from sources including MIS Quarterly and PubMed. The results emphasize that in order to promote broad adoption, user-friendly interfaces, improved digital literacy, and strong support networks are required. By offering prompt and efficient healthcare services, telehealth may enhance the quality of life for older adults in Nigeria with the help of legislative support and smart investments in telehealth infrastructure.

Keywords: Telehealth, chronic disease management, older adults, Technology Acceptance Model, perceived usefulness.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and heart disease are growing increasingly prevalent worldwide. According to WHO (2016), chronic diseases account for 57% of all illnesses and more than 75% of all deaths. According to the US Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2015), a chronic illness is one that lasts three months or longer, and the illnesses are referred to as chronic diseases and affect mostly the elderly. As the global population ages, the elderly become increasingly vulnerable to long-term medical issues. In the United States, more than 80% of the elderly (55 and older) have at least one chronic ailment, with 68% having two or more (Koch, 2016). Chronic problems, which are typically

incurable, can have a significant impact on the health, emotions, financial position, and quality of life of older people and their families. Chronic disease and impairment have recently been reported in a significant proportion of Nigerian older adults. Many of them suffer from osteoarthritis and other chronic diseases, which limit their capacity to do everyday tasks and travel (Faronbi & Fajemilehin, 2012). This demography is especially vulnerable in Nigeria, which has limited access to healthcare services, a deteriorating healthcare infrastructure, and a growing demand for age-appropriate care (Akinyemi et al., 2023). Consequently, a paradigm change from a provider-centered approach to a patient-centered management model that puts the needs of the patient first is required in the delivery of health care to the vulnerable. This clearly calls for an alternative in telehealth for the treatment of chronic illnesses in the elderly.

Telehealth is the use of information and communication technology to access clinical and nonclinical health services (Healthit.gov, 2022). It comprises remotely monitoring patients' conditions using audio, video, or other telecommunications technologies (Modglin, 2021). Telehealth removes the long-distance barrier between patient and physician, and enhances patient care, advice, reminders, education, intervention, monitoring, and remote admission (Modglin, 2021). Telehealth, or the delivery of health-related services via telecommunications technology, has the potential to assist older people in managing chronic conditions. Telehealth has been acknowledged for its ability to improve access to treatment, monitor chronic conditions, and provide patient education, especially for individuals living in remote or medically underserved areas (Wootton et al., 2021).

Telehealth has various advantages in mitigating the problems of chronic disease management in older adults (Ronco et al, 2019). First, it allows healthcare practitioners to monitor the health of older adults remotely, decreasing the need for in-person visits. This is especially important in rural regions, where healthcare facilities are frequently faraway from patients' homes (Ronco et al, 2019). Wearable gadgets and Smartphone applications can measure vital signs, glucose levels, and medication adherence remotely, giving healthcare practitioners with real-time data (Zhao et al., 2021). Second, telehealth facilitates ongoing patient education and self-management. Chronic illness management necessitates that older persons actively participate in their treatment by changing their lifestyle, following drug regimen, and checking their health on a regular basis. Telehealth systems may provide personalized educational materials and reminders to encourage self-management, which has been demonstrated to enhance patient outcomes (Wootton et al., 2021). Finally, telemedicine can improve communication between healthcare practitioners and older persons, resulting in more tailored treatment (Timothy et al, 2022).

In Nigeria, where the patient-to-doctor ratio is high, telehealth may alleviate some of the load on healthcare practitioners by allowing for virtual consultations. This can increase the frequency and quality of follow-up treatment, ensuring that older persons get the attention they require to properly manage their diseases. However, for telehealth to be effectively adopted by older adults in Nigeria, understanding their perception of this technology is essential. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis (1989), provides a framework to explore the factors that influence the acceptance and use of new technologies.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to:

1. Assess the Perceived Usefulness (PU) of telehealth in improving health outcomes and reducing healthcare access challenges for older adults in Nigeria.
2. Examine the Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) of telehealth, focusing on accessibility and digital literacy support for older adults.
3. Recommend strategies to enhance telehealth adoption among older Nigerian adults for effective chronic illness management.

Theoretical Framework: Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Over the previous few decades, various models have been developed and used to study information technology adoption and use. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is one of the most widely used

models for investigating the perceptions and variables that impact new technology acceptance. The core idea underlying TAM is that technology adoption is influenced by two factors: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). PU is an individual's conviction that using a given system or technology would improve their performance or outcomes, whereas PEOU is the user's perception of how simple the use of the technology is. Both qualities have been shown to have a significant influence on technology adoption behaviors in a variety of situations, including healthcare (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000; Davis, 1989). In the context of telehealth for chronic illness management among older adults in Nigeria, PU may be described as the perceived benefit of telehealth in terms of improving health outcomes, expanding access to healthcare services, and reducing the burden of travel to healthcare facilities. PEOU refers to the ease and use of telehealth services, especially for elderly people who may be unfamiliar with technology.

Perceived Usefulness (PU) in Telehealth

To further comprehend the basic component of TAM—Perceived Usefulness (PU)—in the context of telehealth adoption among older persons, the following sub-themes will be discussed:

Sub-themes for Perceived Usefulness (PU):

Enhancing Health Outcomes

Reducing Travel and Healthcare Access Challenges

Enhancing Health Outcomes

One of the main factors influencing the acceptance of telehealth is the perceived improvement in health outcomes. For older adults with chronic conditions, telehealth offers an opportunity to receive continuous monitoring and care, which can lead to better health management. Telehealth is an effective tool to monitor patients and support self-management and self-monitoring (Lillicrap et al, 2021), thereby enhancing the feeling of safety at home (Azad et al, 2012). Additionally, telehealth has the potential to support health care delivery and fulfill health care needs in patients by tracking patients' data remotely and intervene promptly to chronic diseases at all levels of care (Powers et al, 2017), particularly in those receiving home-based treatments such as continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis [CAPD] (Azad et al, 2012). Furthermore, In Nigeria, where access to healthcare facilities is often limited, telehealth can provide older adults with the means to maintain regular contact with healthcare providers, potentially reducing complications associated with chronic diseases. For telehealth to be widely accepted by older adults in Nigeria, it must demonstrate clear benefits in terms of improving their health and well-being. This aligns with the concept of PU, as older adults are more likely to adopt telehealth if they believe that it will lead to better health outcomes and improved quality of life.

Reducing Travel and Healthcare Access Challenges

In addition to health outcomes, PU in the context of telehealth is also linked to the convenience it offers by reducing the need for physical travel to healthcare facilities. Many older adults in Nigeria live in rural areas, where healthcare infrastructure is limited, and access to medical care often requires long-distance travel. Telehealth eliminates the need for these trips, enabling older adults to access healthcare services from the comfort of their homes. The perceived convenience of telehealth is a significant factor in its acceptance, as it saves time, effort, and money, especially for older adults with mobility issues (Frennert et al., 2020). As healthcare access remains a challenge in Nigeria, particularly for older adults in remote regions, telehealth presents an invaluable solution. The perceived usefulness of this technology in addressing access challenges and improving the continuity of care can greatly influence its adoption among older adults.

Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) in Telehealth

Similarly, to explore Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), the following subthemes were identified:

User-Friendly Interface

Training and Support for Older Adults

User-Friendly Interfaces

The adoption of telehealth by older persons is largely dependent on perceived ease of use, or PEOU. Older persons are less likely to use telehealth platforms and technologies if they are challenging to use. Therefore, accessibility and ease of use must be given top priority in the design of telehealth systems. For older persons to utilize telehealth platforms without major difficulties, user-friendly interfaces with large writing, clear directions, and intuitive navigation are crucial (Lee et al., 2019). Digital technology is unfamiliar to many elderly individuals, especially those in rural Nigeria. Complex telehealth systems may thus scare them or deter them from utilizing the service. Studies show that providing technical support and simplifying telehealth platforms might boost older adults' adoption of telehealth (Cimperman et al., 2016).

Digital Literacy and Support Systems

Helping elderly adults access telehealth services is another crucial PEOU element. Many older adults may need help from caregivers, community health workers, or family members when using telehealth platforms. Offering a support system can boost perceived ease of use. In the view of Chen & Chan (2014), older adults' awareness of available assistance propels a more willingness to use telehealth services. Hence, telehealth assistance service is a necessity, for older adults in Nigeria, whose digital literacy is often low, to get more used to telehealth technology. Also, it is imperative to equip them with training and tools. Initiatives to boost digital literacy and continuous technical assistance can considerably improve the perceived usability of telehealth platforms, increasing the use of telehealth platforms by older persons.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Telehealth has the potential to improve chronic illness treatment for Nigerian elderly by boosting access to care, enhancing patient self-management, and enabling continuous monitoring of health issues. However, its success is dependent on overcoming infrastructural, computer literacy, and healthcare professional training challenges. With targeted investments and legislative support, telehealth has the potential to greatly enhance the quality of life for older Nigerians suffering from chronic diseases. There is therefore the need for innovative approaches to health management that can improve access to care, ensure continuity of treatment, and enhance patient outcomes. Telehealth presents a promising solution to address these challenges, particularly for older adults who often face barriers to accessing in-person care due to mobility issues, limited transportation, and geographic constraints.

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